

Learned Long-Term Stability Scan Filtering for Robust Robot Localisation in Continuously Changing Environments

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Abstract—In field robotics, particularly in the agricultural sector, precise localization presents a challenge due to the constantly changing nature of the environment. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping algorithms can provide an effective estimation of a robot’s position, but their long-term performance may be impacted by false data associations. Additionally, alternative strategies such as the use of RTK-GPS can also have limitations, such as dependence on external infrastructure. To address these challenges, this paper introduces a novel stability scan filter. This filter can learn and infer the motion status of objects in the environment, allowing it to identify the most stable objects and use them as landmarks for robust robot localization in a continuously changing environment. The proposed method involves an unsupervised point-wise labelling of LiDAR frames by utilizing temporal observations of the environment, as well as a regression network called Long-Term Stability Network (LTS-NET) to learn and infer 3D LiDAR points long-term motion status. Experiments demonstrate the ability of the stability scan filter to infer the motion stability of objects on a real agricultural long-term dataset. Results show that by only utilizing points belonging to long-term stable objects, the localization system exhibits reliable and robust localization performance for long-term missions compared to using the entire LiDAR frame points.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate and reliable localization is essential for the autonomous navigation of robots and self-driving vehicles, particularly in environments that undergo significant changes [1], such as agricultural fields (Fig. 1). The Real-Time Kinematic Global Positioning System (RTK-GPS) is a widely used localization technique in field robotics, where high precision is required. RTK-GPS can provide localization accuracy of up to a few centimeters by using a combination of satellite-based positioning and ground-based reference stations [2]. However, RTK-GPS systems come with certain limitations such as high cost, reliance on subscriptions and external infrastructure, susceptibility to environmental factors and weather conditions, which can lead to degraded performance and reliability.

As an alternative, localization methods based on map building from onboard sensors, such as cameras [3] or LiDAR [4], may offer more robust and accurate solutions at a lower cost. LiDAR sensors, in particular, provide precise range information and has been found to be more robust than camera-based localization, as it is immune to changes in illumination and can provide accurate range information even in low-

Fig. 1: The images show a visual comparison of the significant changes in an outdoor agricultural orchard throughout the season. The image on the left represents the initial stage of the environment when deploying the robot in March, and the right image represents the fully grown stage in June [5].

light conditions [6]. In this work, we focus on LiDAR-based localization and its potential as a more reliable for autonomous navigation in continuously changing environments such as agricultural fields.

In agricultural environments or outdoor fields in general, map-based localization systems often fail to perform reliable localization for long-term missions over extended periods of time (such as months or even years) due to constant changes in the environment [7], resulting in the initial map becoming quickly outdated. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithms have demonstrated robust performance in estimating the robot pose in dynamic environments [8]. However, they are often prone to failure when used for long-term operations due to false positives in data association between localization sessions. False positive cases occur when an incorrect match is made between an object in the environment and a sensor measurement, which is due to significant changes between the map and the measurements. This problem has been well documented in literature, for example in [9].

Despite the changes that could occur in the environment, some parts of it remain static, which could be used as a landmark for achieving accurate and reliable long-term localization. We hypothesise that a learned filter, capable of distinguishing between static and dynamic parts of a scene, will significantly enhance long-term localization accuracy by reducing the impact of dynamic objects. To achieve this, we propose an unsupervised scan filter learning for robust robot localisation in long-term changing environments. This method leverages previous observations to recognize objects

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Fig. 2: The BLT-Dataset was used to create a LiDAR scan visualization. The left image shows an aerial view of the scan location, highlighting the stable structures in the environment. The middle image is the raw scan. The right image displays the predicted spatial-temporal stability labels from LTS-NET, with points inferred into these categories: (a) fast-moving objects such as humans, (b) visual appearance changing objects like seasonal vegetation changes, (c) ground plane points, and (d) long-term stable points like those belonging to a building.

that maintain stability over time and generates training data for a deep learning model. This model can then be used on future scans to directly identify stable objects within 3D LiDAR frames as illustrated in Fig. 2, allowing us to filter out dynamic points and rely on stable structures for extended localization.

Our key contributions in this paper include: (1) an automated point-wise labelling method for LiDAR scans. (2) The Long-Term Stability Network (LTS-NET), a regression network designed to infer LiDAR points spatiotemporal stability. (3) An analysis of a real-world long-term vineyard dataset shows that using filtered scans enhances the accuracy and robustness of 3D LiDAR localization algorithms that use scan matching techniques, compared to using raw scans. (4) We show that the trained regression model can directly predict objects’ stability in a new environment without the need for a prior sequence of temporal observations.

II. RELATED WORK

There have been numerous approaches proposed for long-term localization, ranging from traditional methods based on odometry and map-based approaches to more recent approaches that utilize deep learning techniques.

One common approach to long-term localization is to use a pre-built map of the environment and match current sensor readings to the map to determine the robot’s position. This approach can be effective in environments with stable, distinct features, but can be less reliable in environments with more dynamic or changing features. To address this limitation, some studies have explored the use of additional structural information in the initial map to increase robustness, such as Gaussian Mixture probabilistic maps [10]. Others have extracted pole-like landmarks for long-term localization [11].

In some approaches to long-term localization, the map is updated to reflect changes in the environment. Researchers have addressed this in several ways. For instance, some studies have

accumulated visual experience of the same place over time and used it for localization [12], [13]. This approach has been shown to handle some level of environmental change, but can lead to very large map sizes. Other solutions have employed mathematical models to predict changes in the environment [14], [15]. For example, FreMEn [14] is a frequency map enhancement approach that considers regular feature points in visual SLAM as a combination of harmonic functions. This method has been shown to improve robot localization in indoor environments.

Another approach to long-term localization is the use of temporal mapping, which involves building a temporary map when global matching is unreliable and merging it with a pre-built map for use in later localization runs [16]. However, this approach may not be suitable for continuously changing environments as the appearance can change dramatically, requiring the method to enter the mapping phase repeatedly.

Recent advancements in long-term localization rely on the utilization of deep learning models for extracting long-term stable features, which could be either from 3D point cloud data [17], [18] or visual data [19], [20]. The models can be trained to identify stable features in the environment, such as tree trunks or light posts, and use them as landmarks for achieving long-term localization. However, these methods primarily target urban structures and require manual annotation of data for model training. The agricultural domain has seen the development of visual localization and mapping techniques to identify specific environmental features such as tree trunks [21], [22]. These methods facilitate long-term operations but are limited by the need for manual data annotation which is prone to human error and time-consuming [23]. Additionally, visual data is vulnerable to changes in lighting conditions [6].

In this paper, our method differs from existing state of the art methods by eliminating the need for costly manual annotation in labelling LiDAR frames. Our approach is data-

Fig. 3: The unsupervised data labelling pipeline for 3D LiDAR frames $\mathbf{S} : \{S_0, \dots, S_n\}$. First we build a point cloud map \mathbf{M}_k using a SLAM system, then we assign the long-term stability labels to \mathbf{M}_k by exploring the previous maps $\mathbf{M}_{0:k-1}$. Finally the stability labels are projected back to the LiDAR frames by using these poses $T_{0:n}^{W_k}$.

driven and capable of adapting to any environment. It leverages the temporal characteristics of the environment’s history to train a deep learning model, enabling it to learn about the long-term stability of objects directly from LiDAR frames.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

We propose a generic learnable stability scan filter to learn and extract the inherent stable structure (i.e. landmarks) of a given environment from 3D LiDAR scans, then filter other objects to achieve robust localization over extended periods of time. To accomplish this, we utilize a temporal sequence of 3D point cloud maps $\mathbf{M}_{0:k}$, and their associated LiDAR frames $\{\mathbf{S}\}_{0:k}$. Our framework consists of an algorithm for assigning spatiotemporal features for \mathbf{M}_k with respect to previous observations $\mathbf{M}_{0:k-1}$, then projecting those features back to their associated LiDAR frames $\{\mathbf{S}\}_k$. Second, a neural network, $f(\cdot)$, that learns the spatiotemporal features (i.e. stability score) from the labelled LiDAR frames to predict the spatiotemporal features of the next session $\{\mathbf{S}\}_{k+1}$.

A. Automated labelling of 3D LiDAR frames

Manual labelling of 3D LiDAR frames can be a challenging and time-consuming task, especially when dealing with large volumes of data [23]. It requires a significant amount of human effort, and there is always the risk of human error. Moreover, the type of labels applied to the point cloud of LiDAR frames varies depending on the targeted application. For instance, semantic segmentation tasks may benefit from full class segmentation, while tasks such as distinguishing moving from stable objects may only require binary labels. In this work, we investigate the utilization of continuous labels to represent the spatiotemporal stability of the point cloud.

The continuous labels are assigned based on the points of a spatiotemporal dependency across multiple time slices of the environment. The spatiotemporal information can capture objects’ long-term motion status. To label the LiDAR frames, we first build a point cloud for all the observations, perform the labelling on them, then we project the labels back to the frames. The pipeline is summarized in Fig. 3, here the process in more detail.

Maps labelling To accurately label points in the map based on their long-term stability, our approach requires at least two observations of the environment. Given the LiDAR frames $\mathbf{S} : \{S_0, \dots, S_n\}$ (n is the number of the frames) and IMU data for each observation, we first build a point cloud map using mapping system (such as FAST-LIO [8]), and we save the transformation matrix $T_{0:n}^{W_k} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ for each LiDAR frame, where W_k is the world frame of the point cloud map k .

Second, while building the point cloud map, we also construct an occupancy probability map using OctoMap [24]. This step allows for the representation of uncertainty about the state of the environment, which is useful when calculating the points’ features at later stages. The resulted point cloud map with its occupancy probability is represented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}_k &= \{\mathbf{P}_1, \mathbf{P}_2, \dots, \mathbf{P}_m\}, \\ \rho(\mathbf{P}) &= p(\mathbf{P}|\mathbf{O}_k), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)$, $\mathbf{P}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the 3D coordinate of the i -th point, m is the total number of points, \mathbf{O}_k is the octree data structure that represents the 3D occupancy grid and $\rho(\mathbf{P})$ is the probability of a point location exists in a given state (occupied, free or unknown) based on \mathbf{O}_k , where unknown in this context means that the location of the point was either not scanned or occluded by other objects.

Then we segment the ground plane using the Cloth Simulation Filter (CSF) [25], where $\mathbf{M}_k^{OG}, \mathbf{M}_k^G = CSF(\mathbf{M}_k)$ that is **Off-Ground** and **Ground** maps respectively. We assign a value of 0 to all ground points to ensures the points are labelled with the same value (the labelled ground is denoted as $\mathbf{M}_k^{G,L}$), and segmenting \mathbf{M}_k^G increases the disparity when calculating the points’ features at later stages for the off ground maps.

To ensure robust data association between the temporal observations, we geometrically align all the off-ground point cloud maps w.r.t the initial off-ground map. To achieve that we utilize the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) [26] algorithm to perform the registration (i.e. alignment) process. The resulting transformation matrix $T_{M_k^{OG} M_0^{OG}}^{M_0^{OG}}$, where M_k^{OG} and M_0^{OG} denote the off-ground point cloud maps of the k -th and initial point

cloud map respectively, is then used to transform the nodes of the associated octomap \mathbf{O}_k and the labelled ground plane $\mathbf{M}_k^{G,L}$ to the new coordinates of the transformed map.

In the next step, we extract the stability features, referred to as labels, from the off-ground point cloud maps. The process of feature extraction, also known as labelling, is outlined in Algorithm. 1. Initially, we select a map to be labelled (\mathbf{M}_k^{OG}). For each point $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbf{M}_k^{OG}$, we first find the occupancy probability $\rho(\mathbf{P})$ of the point location in occupancy grid \mathbf{O}_i of the query map \mathbf{M}_i^{OG} , if the location is not occluded we find the closest point \mathbf{q} using k-Nearest Neighbors (*KNN*) algorithm, then we compute the spatial distance (d) between \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{q} and append it to the distance vector $\mathbf{d} = [\mathbf{d}, d]$. On the other hand, if the point location was occluded, we append -1 to the distance vector $\mathbf{d} = [\mathbf{d}, -1]$. After querying all other maps, the point label l of \mathbf{P} is set using the maximum spatial distance of \mathbf{d} as a feature, then we map the value using the cumulative distribution function of an exponential function as follows:

$$\mathbf{P}.l = 1 - e^{-\max(\mathbf{d})}, \quad (2)$$

where the final label value is a score bounded between 0 and 1 indicating the point spatiotemporal stability.

At the end of the labelling process, the labeled map may contain some noise due to occlusion or mislabeled points. To fix this, we introduce a Voting Median Filter (VMF) based on the labels of nearest neighbors points:

$$f_{med}(i) = \text{median}\{l_j \mid j \in \mathcal{NN}_i(kn)\}, \quad (3)$$

$f_{med}(i)$ is the filtered label for the point \mathbf{P}_i , l_j is the label of the point \mathbf{P}_j , $\mathcal{NN}_i(kn)$ is the set of kn nearest neighbors of point \mathbf{P}_i , and median is the median function that returns the middle value of a set of values. An illustration of the impact of applying VMF on the labelled map is presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: The impact of applying the VMF on the raw spatiotemporal feature map can be seen on the right, resulting from the input on the left which depicts part of a building.

Finally, the filtered labeled off-ground map will be combined with the corresponding ground point cloud map $\mathbf{M}_k^{G,L}$, to form the final labelled map $\mathbf{M}_k^L = \mathbf{M}_k^{OG,L} \cup \mathbf{M}_k^{G,L}$, which will be used for labelling the LiDAR frames. In summary our approach for labelling the points is based on the assumption that long-term stable objects should appear in the same geometrical location across all temporal observations, thus the associated label value should be smaller compared to dynamic objects.

LiDAR frames labelling: To propagate the features/labels from the labelled map \mathbf{M}_k^L back to its LiDAR frames \mathbf{S} :

Algorithm 1: Unsupervised point-wise labelling algorithm

inputs: A set of filtered and aligned maps $\mathbf{M}_{0:k}^{OG}$

output: A labeled map \mathbf{M}_k^L

foreach $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbf{M}_k^{OG}$ **do**

Initialize closest distance vector: $\mathbf{d} = \{\}$

foreach $\mathbf{M}_i^{OG} \in \mathbf{M}_{0:k-1}^{OG}$ **do**

if $p(\mathbf{P}|\mathbf{O}_i) \neq \text{Unknown}$ **then**

$\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \text{KNN}(\mathbf{M}_i^{OG}, \mathbf{P})$

$\mathbf{d}.append(\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 (q_i - p_i)^2})$

else

$\mathbf{d}.append(-1) \triangleright \mathbf{P}$ is occluded in \mathbf{M}_i^{OG}

Point label: $\mathbf{P}.l = 1 - e^{-\max(\mathbf{d})}$

Filter $\mathbf{M}_k^{OG,L}$ using median filter Eq. 3

$\mathbf{M}_k^L = \mathbf{M}_k^{OG,L} \cup \mathbf{M}_k^{G,L}$

$\{\mathcal{S}_0, \dots, \mathcal{S}_n\}$, we first transform the frame \mathcal{S}_i coordinate to its associated map \mathbf{M}_k^L coordinate using the transformation matrix $T_{\mathbf{M}_k^{OG}}^{M_0^{OG}} \cdot T_i^{W_k}$, where $i \in n$ is the frame number. Then, we use nearest-neighbour interpolation to propagate the labels back to the frame. Finally, we transform the frame back to its original coordinates.

B. LTS-NET

We present the Long-Term Stability NETWORK (LTS-NET) Fig. 5, a regression network that is capable of learning the spatiotemporal labels from the auto labelling algorithm directly on point cloud data. LTS-NET utilize the PointNet++ architecture [27], which has been shown to be effective in processing point cloud data directly. The input to the LTS-NET is a 3D LiDAR frame, represented as sets of 3D point coordinates $\mathcal{S}_i : \{(x_0, y_0, z_0), \dots, (x_{nn}, y_{nn}, z_{nn})\}$, where nn is the number of points in the frame (we only utilize the points coordinates as a features).

LTS-NET Encoder: In the encoder component, we employ 4 abstraction layers (down-sampling and feature concatenation layers) to aggregate local features from the previous layer into a global feature representation for each point set. To maintain consistent abstraction across layers and prevent information loss or distortion due to varying levels of down-sampling, we use equal numbers of input points in the first two layers (2048 points) and in the last two layers (1024 points). The features sampling radius for each input point across the layers is set to 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, and 1 m, respectively, to facilitate the learning of local geometry and its spatiotemporal stability

LTS-NET Decoder: In the decoder, we use 4 feature propagation layers (up-sampling layers) to restore point features from a down-sampled point cloud to its original form. This layer takes the global features from the previous layer and updates the features of each point by considering its local neighborhood.

The final output layer uses a Sigmoid function to bound the output values between 0 and 1. To supervise the training

Fig. 5: The LTS-NET is a point-wise network designed to infer spatiotemporal stability of 3D LiDAR frames. The input frames \mathcal{S}_i are processed by SDL, which divides the frame into a predefined number of slices, \mathcal{N} , as expressed in Eq. 5. The SDL passes each slice, s_j , to the network for processing. The slices are then merged at the output of the network to form the original frame. This allows the network to infer the spatiotemporal stability of each point in the frame accurately.

process, we used the Root Mean Square Error as a cost function, given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (l_i - \hat{l}_i)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (4)$$

here N is the number of points that goes into the first layer of LTS-NET multiplied by the training batch size, l_i and \hat{l}_i are the true and predicted stability values of the i -th point.

LiDAR frames data loader: to process the LiDAR frame effectively by the network, we introduce the Slices Data Loader (SDL). The SDL divides the LiDAR frame into \mathcal{N} slices, with a slice angle of $\psi = 2\pi/\mathcal{N}$, where $\mathcal{N} \geq 1$. The slice points are found by using the azimuthal angle θ of the spherical coordinates of the LiDAR frame, which is calculated as $\theta = \arctan2(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x})$, where \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x} are the Cartesian coordinates of the frame points. The slice points s_j are then obtained using the following equation:

$$s_j = (\mathcal{S} | (\theta \geq \phi(j)) \cap (\theta < \Phi(j))), \quad (5)$$

where $j \in \mathcal{N}$ is the slice number, \mathcal{S} is the LiDAR frame and $\phi(j) = j \times \psi$ and $\Phi(j) = (j + 1) \times \psi$. Using the SDL enables the network to effectively learn regression by capturing most frame features. It prevents sub-sampling issues in the initial layer and avoids enlarging model layers, making it less resource-intensive and easier to train on mobile platforms.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset

To demonstrate the effectiveness of our system in learning stable objects and achieving robust localization in a seasonally changing environment, we conducted experiments using the Bacchus Long-Term (BLT) dataset [5]. This dataset was collected in a semi-structured agricultural setting, specifically a vineyard, and includes data captured over a period of several months. During this time, the robot traversed a set of paths that intersected with each other, making it an ideal testbed for evaluating long-term localization algorithms. The traversed

paths in the dataset are presented as a topological map in Fig. 6. The environment in the dataset includes a variety of objects that change at different rates, including static objects like buildings and other structures, slow dynamic objects such as vegetation, and fast dynamic objects like people who accompanied the robot during the data collection sessions.

The mobile robot in the BLT dataset is equipped with various sensors, including an RTK-GPS and an OS1-16 LiDAR sensor. The full list of sensors can be found in [5]. During the experiments, the RTK-GPS was used as the ground truth signal for the robot’s pose, while data from the OS1-16 LiDAR sensor was used to test algorithms. The test path is $B \rightarrow G \rightarrow H \rightarrow C$ as shown in Fig. 6, which have a total length of 105 m. The experiments were conducted on six different sessions in 2022: *April 6th*, *April 20th*, *June 1st*, *June 8th*, *June 29th*, and *July 13th*. We use *April 6th* data to create the base map for localizing in the subsequent session.

Fig. 6: The topological map for the traversed paths in BLT-Dataset. The traversed path that we used for our experiments is highlighted in red.

The data labelling is performed as explained in Sec. III-A, then the labelled data is used to train a deep regression model to be used later to infer the stable points of the data (LiDAR frames) of the upcoming session. For instance, the labelled data of *June 1st* is labelled w.r.t previous two sessions that are *April 6th* and *April 20th*, then we train the network, in which we call LTS-JUNE-1 (based on the training data), to infer the long term stable objects of the next session *June 8th* LiDAR frames.

To evaluate the performance of the network, we used two metrics: root mean squared error loss (\mathcal{L}) and the coefficient of determination, also known as R-Squared (\mathcal{R}^2), which is often considered a more meaningful metric for evaluating regression models [28]:

$$\mathcal{R}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{l}_i - \bar{l})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (l_i - \bar{l})^2}, \quad (6)$$

here N represents the number of labels, l_i is the label value for the i -th point, \hat{l}_i is the predicted label value from the network, and \bar{l} is the mean of the ground truth labels.

LTS-NET training: To train the network, we split the LiDAR frames of the sessions into 80% training and 20% validation data. The training was conducted on a workstation with an Intel Core i7-6850K CPU, 64GB of RAM, and two NVidia GTX 1080ti GPUs with 12GB of RAM each. The

model was implemented using the PyTorch framework. We used an initial learning rate of 0.001, momentum of 0.9, and trained the model for 90 epochs for each network. The training time for the models was approximately 40 hours. The training results are summarized in Tab. I.

TABLE I: Networks training performance on different sessions. The metrics represent the average value.

Network	Training session	\mathcal{L}	\mathcal{R}^2
LTS-APRIL-20	April 20th	0.124	0.784
LTS-JUNE-1	June 1st	0.127	0.897
LTS-JUNE-8	June 8th	0.131	0.888
LTS-JUNE-29	June 29th	0.114	0.916

LTS-NET inference: Table II summarizes the network’s inference performance on different sessions. As shown, LTS-APRIL-20 network had a poor performance with a negative R-Squared value, indicating that it was unable to accurately explain the data from *June 1st*. This may be due to the significant time gap between *April 20th* and *June 1st*, which resulted in a significant change in the appearance of the environment due to plant growth. However, the performance improved for the subsequent sessions as the appearance of the environment remained similar.

TABLE II: Networks inference performance on different sessions. The metrics represent the average value.

Network	Inferred session	\mathcal{L}	\mathcal{R}^2
LTS-APRIL-20	June 1st	0.427	-0.200
LTS-JUNE-1	June 8th	0.238	0.618
LTS-JUNE-8	June 29th	0.231	0.642
LTS-JUNE-29	July 13th	0.221	0.680

B. Evaluating localization performance

To evaluate the effect of filtering dynamics from LiDAR scans on long-term localization performance, we compare the localization performance of the filtered scans with that of the raw scans. All localization experiments were performed on an off-ground static map from *April 6th* as a base/reference map. The off-ground map used because the ground plane does not provide unique features for achieving long-term localization and can potentially lead to incorrect convergence of the localization package due to its size compared to the rest of the map. Therefore, we filter it out of the base map.

For localization, we use the HDL localization package ¹, which is a 3D localizer based on the Normal Distribution Transform (NDT) [29] method. The filtered scans were obtained by thresholding the network predictions. During our experiments, we found that a threshold of $\epsilon_1 = 0.9$ is sufficient to filter out slow and fast dynamic points.

To evaluate the performance of the localizer, we use the Mean and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE), which measures the difference

between a device’s true and estimated trajectories in a global coordinate system [30]. The true (ground truth) position in our setup is the pose from RTK GPS. Table III summarize the localization performance.

The metrics presented in Table III provide information on the accuracy of the system, but do not reflect its robustness. To evaluate the robustness of the system, we use the empirical Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). This metric is commonly used to assess the registration accuracy between a reference scan and an input scan, as explained in [31]. However, it can also be used to assess the robustness of a localization system, as demonstrated in [32]. The CDF plots for the translational and rotational errors are presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: The CDF plot is comparing the localization translation and rotational error of raw scans to the localization translation error of filtered scans for different sessions.

C. Results discussion

The localization performance for the *April 20th* session was evaluated using raw scans only as it was the second session, and there were not enough observations to train a network to infer *April 20th* scans. The localization performance was still the best among all sessions because the appearance of the environment did not change much between *April 20th* and *April 6th*. For the reset of the sessions the filtered scans resulted in improved robustness and performance for the localizer, as presented in Tab. III and in figure 7. However, on *June 1st* the localization performance was similar for both raw and filtered scans due to the failure of the LTS-APRIL-20 network to infer dynamic points in the LiDAR scans of *June 1st*, with identical CDF plots for both scans types. We attribute this to the lack of examples of dynamic objects/structures in the April data, as the vineyard was only in the early stages of vegetation at that time.

For the *June 8th* localization session, the LTS-JUNE-1 model demonstrated slight improvement in localization robustness and accuracy, with a mean error of 0.216 m for the entire estimated trajectory compared to 0.228 m for the raw scans. The raw scans showed good performance, which can be explained by a trimming process that occurred between *June 1st* and *June 8th*, resulting in fewer dynamic objects in the environment as shown in Figure 8. On *June 29th*, the filtered scans demonstrated superior performance and robustness compared to the raw scans. For example, the mean

¹https://github.com/koide3/hdl_localization

TABLE III: Localization performance for robot position (pos) estimation of the raw scans compared the filtered scans. The metrics used are RMSE, Mean and std of the ATE, the units are all in m.

Session	Raw		Network	Filtered	
	ATE_{pos}^{RMSE}	ATE_{pos}^{Mean} (std)		ATE_{pos}^{RMSE}	ATE_{pos}^{Mean} (std)
<i>April 20th</i>	0.186	0.179 (0.048)	—	—	—
<i>June 1st</i>	1.206	0.743 (0.951)	LTS-APRIL-20	1.176	0.731 (0.921)
<i>June 8th</i>	0.300	0.228 (0.195)	LTS-JUNE-1	0.239	0.216 (0.103)
<i>June 29th</i>	2.994	1.250 (2.721)	LTS-JUNE-8	0.890	0.395 (0.795)
<i>July 13th</i>	2.199	0.903 (2.005)	LTS-JUNE-29	0.295	0.234 (0.179)

localization error for the entire trajectory was less than 0.4 m for the filtered scans, while it was 1.25 m for the raw scans. Similar results were observed on *July 13th*, indicating that the LTS-NET was able to successfully identify and filter in the long-term stable objects.

(a) Vine rows for *June 1st* (b) Vine rows for *June-8th*

Fig. 8: Comparison between the orchard rows in *June 1st* and *June-8th* indicating that a pruning process occurred between the two sessions, which resulted in fewer dynamic elements.

Despite the fact that the translational error was smaller for the filtered scans, the rotation error was similar for both types of scans, as illustrated in Fig. 7. This can be attributed to the robot’s movement pattern, which consisted of traversing in straight lines within the rows of vines and only performing rotations at the end of the rows where stable structures were more pronounced. This enabled the localizer to robustly estimate the robot’s heading angle for both types of scans.

D. Evaluating LTS-NET inference in a new environment

The motivation behind this experiment is to evaluate the performance of LTS-NET which has been trained on the temporal stack data from the BLT dataset in a completely new vineyard environment. The aim is to demonstrate that once the LTS-NET has learned long-term spatiotemporal stability, it can be applied directly in a new environment that lacks prior observations. To this end, data were collected in an initial-state vineyard (as shown in Fig. 9), over two sessions, primarily to generate labels for evaluating the LTS-NET’s inference performance. The results show that the network exhibits an acceptable evaluation loss ($\mathcal{L} = 0.245$) and coefficient of determination ($\mathcal{R}^2 = 0.216$) in this new environment. This suggests that the model is capable of providing plausible estimates of object stability, as demonstrated in Fig. 9-d, where the model correctly identifies the human as a dynamic object and the poles in Fig. 9-e as static/stable objects.

Fig. 9: Using the regression model learned from the BLT dataset in a new vineyard setting. (a) The image of the new field. (b) Displays a LiDAR frame with its predicted points stability labels. (c) A zoomed-in photo highlights some of the inferred features. (d) The individual accompanying the robot is considered dynamic based on inference. (e) The poles in the environment are considered stable objects through inference.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a novel spatiotemporal data-driven point-wise filter for learning long-term stability landmarks for robust localization in a continuously changing environment. The system utilizes an unsupervised labelling algorithm for 3D LiDAR scans to generate spatiotemporal point-wise stability scores based on multiple observations of the environment, and a point-wise regression network called LTS-NET to infer the stability of objects from 3D LiDAR frames. Through experimental evaluation, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of our approach in filtering dynamic elements from the scans and achieving robust, long-term localization performance. Furthermore, LTS-NET showed good performance when inferring object stability on LiDAR data from a completely new environment.

While the system demonstrated the ability to learn long-term stable features and use them to achieve robust localization over time, there are still some limitations that could potentially compromise the overall system. These limitations

can be summarized as follows: (1) Our unsupervised labelling algorithm relies on the accuracy of ICP map alignment; thus if this step fails, incorrect features may be associated with the points, which will impact the learning and filtering process. This issue could be addressed by introducing some manual intervention by a human operator. (2) The LiDAR resolution is another factor that affects the robustness of the system. A higher resolution allows the system to extract and learn more stable features, resulting in increased robustness. (3) The current implementation of LTS-NET has an inference time of approximately 2 frames per second.

As for future work, we aim to optimize the LTS-NET network architecture and code to enable real-time performance. In addition to that, further qualitative analysis is required to verify the transferability of the model to different domains, particularly with regard to seasonal changes, as the necessary data is currently unavailable.

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